

Threading the needle on Traceability within the PABS System – Promoting Equity and Science

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Abstract

Reconciling divergent positions on traceability of sequence information and open access to data will be key if the Pathogen Access and Benefit Sharing negotiations are to be concluded successfully. Convergence might be facilitated by considering related issues such as the risk of jurisdiction shopping, challenges with legal enforcement in scientific infrastructures, interoperability of data and databases, and capacity gaps in access and use of pathogen data in resource limited settings. We apply a scientific lens to provide eight recommendations that harness existing scientific infrastructure and suggest traceability measures that are compatible with open access to sequence information. These recommendations are intended to strengthen pandemic prevention, preparedness and response as well as the equitable sharing of benefits.

Executive Summary

The hard-fought World Health Organization Pandemic Agreement adopted at the 78th World Health Assembly cannot become a reality until the Pathogen Access and Benefit Sharing (PABS) system is successfully agreed. The PABS system must strengthen the scientific ecosystem that delivers knowledge and vaccines, therapeutics and diagnostics (VTDs) and provide legally binding commitments that lead to equitable benefit-sharing, including the sharing of VTDs, while minimizing loopholes. Finding synergies between traceability and open access in support of the PABS system might enable the final puzzle pieces of the negotiation to fall into place. Here, we focus on PABS sequence information (SI) from a research and data management perspective, and assess traceability and open access to data, as set out in Article 12(3) of the Pandemic Agreement. We ask if and how traceability can be implemented without unintended adverse consequences. Our analysis leads to eight inter-related recommendations that promote equitable and accountable benefit sharing, as well as scientific advancement and our collective ability to prepare for and respond to future pandemics.

1. **The risk of jurisdiction shopping.** The PABS system should be easy to use and hard to avoid. 'Open access' pathogen SI will continue to exist due to a number of reasons. Legal fragmentation into 'controlled access' and 'open access' pathogen SI will occur if traceability is operationalized at the level of data access through controlled access databases. Ironically, controlled access will unintentionally lead to major loopholes and jurisdiction shopping because it will create a competitive data market where open data is free from legal obligations and competes with controlled access databases, which can be avoided. Furthermore, if access is the trigger, then only benefits that have been developed using 'controlled access' SI would be captured and shared.

Recommendation 1: Set the scope of PABS to include all publicly available SI from pathogens with pandemic potential, as well as all relevant benefits, including VTDs that were or will be developed from 'open access' or 'old' pathogen SI, repurposed VTDs or VTDs that were developed entirely without the use of PABS material and sequence information. This approach will greatly expand benefit sharing and minimize the risk of jurisdiction shopping.

Recommendation 2: Create incentives for researchers, developers and manufacturers to join the PABS system, for example through linking PABS participation to public funding eligibility or linkage with VTD approval procedures. It will be essential to incentivize companies everywhere, including companies headquartered in non-Member States, for example in the United States of America. Providing clear advantages removes the incentive for jurisdiction shopping.

2. **Scientific infrastructure does not have the capacity for legal enforcement.** Enforcing benefit-sharing obligations through scientific infrastructures through identifying and surveilling users is unprecedented in all current ABS schemes to-date. The responsibility for compliance is on users, authorities and Parties and never on the platforms enabling the exchanges. Many pathogen databases are public entities with limited funding and do not have the legal competency, mandate and capacity to verify and police users. Nor do they exclusively serve PABS users because pathogen data and users are a subset of the life sciences.

Recommendation 3: Define in-scope PABS activities and sectors. Clearly defining which activities and sectors are expected to share VTDs and what events trigger benefit-sharing would enable

identification of entities to sign contracts with WHO. Through the creation of a PABS Advisory Group, a landscape analysis of existing VTDs (and those in the pipeline) could be created in a similar way as is done for the WHO bacterial priority pathogens process.

Recommendation 4: Analyze patents to monitor which VTDs have entered the market from which companies. This information can be used as an indicator to review the effectiveness of the PABS system. Indeed, the Pandemic Influenza Preparedness (PIP) Framework’s open-ended working group suggested a similar procedure for PIP.

3. **Fostering interoperability of data and databases.** Data interoperability is of key importance for pandemic preparedness as researchers need to access and connect different kinds of biological data hosted in many interconnected databases. Controlled access databases cannot be readily connected with other databases due to data sharing restrictions. Decreased interoperability will negatively impact research on pandemic prevention, preparedness and response because information becomes siloed.

Recommendation 5: Support additions to databases and recognize those that adapt towards PABS by asking databases to make information on the PABS system available, to clearly distinguish different contribution types for acknowledgement purposes, to provide unambiguous sample origin information, to not restrict data sharing indefinitely, and to recognize those databases that follow these principles.

Recommendation 6: Promote best citation practice and monitor value by providing guidelines for citation and acknowledgement to make PABS material and SI use visible in publications. Monitor publications as indicators for non-monetary benefit sharing and capacity-building needs.

4. **Improving access and use of pathogen SI in resource limited settings.** Open access and free online bioinformatic tools reduce barriers to conduct pathogen research. If new pathogen SI stays confined to controlled access databases with data sharing restrictions, bioinformatic tools and databases that use data from open access databases will become outdated quickly and eventually unusable. This will especially disadvantage researchers with limited resources or technical training.

Recommendation 7: Strengthen research capacities through binding PABS commitments to increase the capacity of sequencing laboratories, the in-country abilities for bioinformatic analyses, technical training, and the support of research consortia especially in low- and middle-income countries including in inter-pandemic times. These improved research capacities will serve as the knowledge basis for future in-country VTD R&D capabilities.

5. **Greater than the sum of its parts: Supporting multilateralism through open access.** By presenting a comprehensive global biologically diverse dataset, the current open access system adds value to each uploaded SI and supports multilateral benefit-sharing. Currently all publicly available SI from pathogens with pandemic potential (which are not covered by other instruments) are in the scope of the Convention on Biological Diversity’s DSI Multilateral Mechanism (CBD DSI MLM) and its Cali Fund. Neither they nor other international ABS instruments control access to SI or trace access to databases. This risks creating an incompatible benefit-sharing ecosystem.

Recommendation 8: Enable mutual supportiveness with other ABS systems with particular focus on the CBD. Ensure that SI, from pathogens with and without pandemic potential can be used in coherence with the CBD DSI MLM through an open access to data approach. A fully multilateral PABS system, that incorporates pathogen SI in the global, interconnected and open access SI corpus, can support truly multilateral benefit-sharing and enable mutually supportive interactions between ABS systems.

Introduction

In a historic moment for multilateralism, World Health Organization's (WHO) Member States adopted the WHO Pandemic Agreement at the 78th World Health Assembly in May 2025. However, the Agreement will not open for signature until its Pathogen Access and Benefit Sharing (PABS) Annex, outlined in Article 12, has been agreed upon by the open-ended Intergovernmental Working Group (IGWG) and adopted by the World Health Assembly. One of the most challenging aspects of PABS is linked to the Agreement's Article 12, paragraph 3:

*"Taking into account the differences in the use of PABS Materials and Sequence Information, the development of a safe, accountable and transparent PABS System shall address traceability measures and open access to data."*¹

The debate hinges on whether and how to use traceability measures to ensure benefit-sharing from sequence information from pathogens with pandemic potential (hereafter called pathogen SI). We believe that 'traceability' and 'open access to data' can, if carefully implemented, complement each other and support an equitable PABS system.

Pathogen SI is generated once a pathogen's genetic material (DNA or RNA) is extracted and sequenced. SI is used to drive infectious disease research, for example to identify unknown pathogens, support outbreak surveillance and develop vaccines, therapeutics and diagnostics (VTDs). Pathogen SI is fundamentally different to material (physical samples) because SI can only be understood through comparison to other sequences, can be highly repetitive (i.e. non-unique), and is widely and rapidly used, replicated and shared by scientists. Pathogen SI is usually displayed in databases with links to other information and platforms that provide additional information like gene function information, origin information, scientific publications, epidemiological and clinical information², and more.

Pathogen SI is frequently uploaded into open access databases like the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) databases (DDBJ, GenBank, ENA) along with required metadata, including country of origin, provided by the submitter. Predictions of proteins encoded by DNA/RNA are often also submitted and exchanged with yet other databases. SI analysis is a 'big data' field: hundreds of millions of SIs from thousands of organisms are shared and accessed by tens of millions of users and exchanged between thousands of open access databases².

In contrast with standard open science practices, one approach considered during the IGWG negotiations is to control or limit access to pathogen SI to ensure users of pathogen SI can be identified and subsequently use user identities to enforce the PABS system. Controlled access, in contrast to open access, would require databases to register, verify

and report users and restrict onward data sharing. This approach would have adverse consequences and we believe there are other approaches that promote equitable benefit-sharing, in partnership with open science to prepare and protect us from pandemics.

Analysis

1. Solving the risk of jurisdiction shopping

Many PABS discussions presume that Parties will have full control over all PABS SI. This, however, is objectively not the case. Pathogen SI outside of the PABS system, will continue to exist and be accessed through open access databases for the following reasons:

- Pathogens, especially those with pandemic potential, are uncontrollable. They remain within national borders only for a very short period of time. Pathogens are vastly different from, for example, endemic plants that only grow in specific habitats, for which bilateral access and benefit-sharing arrangements were originally developed. Because of their rapid spread, pandemic-causing pathogens will reach the territory of Parties that encourage or require open access and unrestricted data sharing for scientific research outcomes (*vis-à-vis* their funding or publishing rules). For example, the SARS-CoV-2 SI was first shared on 10 January 2020⁴, the PCR test was developed days later, and the first cases in Europe and the United States of America (US), confirmed through PCR testing, were reported around two weeks later⁵. Retrospective testing of samples from sick patients from Europe and the US showed that the virus was already circulating in December 2019^{6,7}. The virus was therefore already out of the country before it was even identified. Thus, had the 10 January sequence been shared only in a controlled access pathogen database, it is clear that researchers would have used alternative patient samples to generate 'open access' sequences. However, it would have taken longer for the world to realize what it was facing if these sequences had been siloed.
- The current pathogen SI databases and their historic ('old') pathogen SI contents will continue to exist and will be used for new research and development (R&D).
- Partners in the INSDC will most likely continue to host their databases⁸ under open access without data sharing restrictions, with many of their established data submitters continuing—legally within their respective jurisdictions—to submit under the open access paradigm.
- States not party to the Pandemic Agreement are likely to pursue bilateral ABS agreements⁹ resulting in a patchwork of different data and benefit-sharing arrangements and *de facto* competition between bilateral and multilateral solutions.

Controlling access to pathogen SI would disconnect it from the mainstream open access (pathogen and other) SI databases, including the INSDC databases. Moreover, it will lead to two types of pathogen SI: 'open access' and 'controlled access'. This will essentially create a competitive market. Users managing legal risk could shop jurisdictions and choose to source pathogen SI from sources that have no or lower benefit-sharing obligations¹⁰. WHO Member States must consider whether the system they create can be readily avoided, whether it is attractive (or not) to use, and whether it would delay the development of VTDs.

Perhaps the most important consideration, though, is whether controlling access will actually deliver VTDs. A PABS system relying on obligations being triggered by whether one has accessed data also means that all VTDs that were developed without access to PABS data would be out of scope. This would significantly reduce the potential pool of VTDs to be shared. This could, for example, pertain to existing and/or repurposed countermeasures like repurposed antiviral drugs. Thus, all VTDs currently approved for pandemic response would not be in scope of an access-triggered PABS system. Only an approach, based on a different trigger, such as the declaration of a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC), including a Pandemic Emergency¹¹, which is agnostic on whether and which pathogen SI or material is used, will enable the inclusion of approved VTDs as well as those that are in the pipeline.

Recommendation 1: Target all relevant SI and benefits.

A PABS scope should be as inclusive as possible extending to all publicly available pathogen SI, including in open access databases, similar to the approach taken by the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in the DSI Multilateral Mechanism (CBD DSI MLM), and would effectively capture pathogen SI everywhere – old and new, open and controlled access.

Secondly, the PABS trigger for sharing benefits should not be access to pathogen SI (which would limit which VTDs are in scope) but rather the PHEIC and/or Pandemic Emergency declarations. This will ensure all VTDs available for pandemic response such as existing antivirals¹² and 'old' vaccines¹³ are immediately available rather than waiting years for new VTDs to be developed.

If the PABS system's trigger for benefit-sharing is based on access to 'new and controlled access' pathogen SI, all VTDs on the market already will not be covered under PABS, which represents a missed opportunity to include potentially decisive countermeasures to fight pandemics.

Recommendation 2: Create incentives for researchers, developers and manufacturers.

Joining the PABS system should come with clear advantages for participants. PABS entities might be given, as a feature of the agreement, access to public research funding, or exclusive access to (joint) procurement from governments or regions, WHO pre-market qualification, pledges from foundations or innovative finance mechanisms, or national product approval procedures. Other forms of incentives could be patent buyouts realized through a separate global fund, Pandemic Preparedness Contracts or Health Impact Financing.

In order for the PABS system to work well at the global level, it should also be attractive for companies headquartered in non-Member States. The Pandemic Influenza Preparedness (PIP) Framework’s Patent analysis (see chapter 2) shows that 48% of the identified (potentially) relevant invention of PIP countermeasures happens in the US¹⁴. A PABS system that provides clear advantages for participants based on incentives, good scientific practice, global public pressure and appeals to corporate responsibility is likely to incentivize companies everywhere to join the PABS system, removing the incentive to ‘jurisdiction shop’.

Science Example

Inmazed, a therapeutic antibody against Ebola infection, was developed using open access pathogen SI of *Orthoebolavirus zairense*. Developers used the new outbreak strain but could have chosen older strains and still have had an effective antibody. If a PABS system both incentivized companies from non-member states to join the PABS system and was triggered by the outbreak of this disease, this therapeutic would be in scope for benefit-sharing. In contrast, in a benefit-sharing model where the trigger is based on the use of ‘new and controlled access’ SI, this would have been very easy to avoid¹⁵.

- [Ebola Virus: Developing a life-saving antibody therapy with public DSI](#)
DSI Scientific Network – Case Study

2. Scientific infrastructure does not have the capacity for legal enforcement

The controlled-access model would require scientific databases to enforce benefit-sharing and trace users of their databases. This would establish the concerning precedent that scientific infrastructures can and should be used for legal enforcement responsibilities. Although pathogen SI-holding databases are willing and able to play a supportive role, a role to enforce obligations through identifying and surveilling users would be

unprecedented and is not found in any ABS scheme to date. ABS has placed responsibility for compliance on users, authorities and Parties and not on the platforms enabling the exchanges. To our knowledge, there is also no precedent for a scientific database or any other scientific infrastructure to legally verify user identity in order to hand over user names and details to a (supranational) authority and liability issues would potentially prohibit them from such activities.

Furthermore, databases do not have the authority to sanction users who infringe on the terms of use or data access agreements without risking legal fallout. This is especially true for the large databases like the INSDC databases that have millions of users around the world. Punishing users through denying access is extremely difficult and resource-intensive to document and enforce in a transparent way. Indeed, this is one reason why the GISAID database has faced significant criticism because access was discontinued in an arbitrary manner¹⁶.

Finally, while some of today's pathogen SI hosting databases are focused on certain pathogens, many others are not. The INSDC databases hold SI from all of biodiversity with only around 8% of SI stemming from viruses and bacteria and around 3% from WHO priority pathogens¹⁷. Accessing these biodiverse databases does not automatically mean that PABS-relevant pathogen SI has been accessed. If the PABS system would require database access tracing, thousands of users, who are not relevant to the PABS system, would be incorrectly captured. But the INSDC databases are essential to the PABS system in order to minimize jurisdiction shopping (see chapter 1), enable interoperability and support researchers in resource-limited settings (see chapter 4).

Recommendation 3: Define activities and sectors in scope.

The PABS system relies on VTD manufacturers signing contracts with the WHO. Instead of using traceability and access to regulate PABS, an alternative would be to align with other ABS instruments and scientific practice by defining the sectors which are in scope of benefit-sharing. For example, the Food and Agriculture Organization's International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA) covers plant genetic resources for food and agriculture *that are used for research, breeding and training*¹⁸. After long negotiations, Parties to the CBD decided not to impose traceability measures for SI. Instead, they took a sector-based approach¹⁹ in which large companies within specific sectors 'benefiting commercially from the use of digital sequence information' are expected to share monetary benefits into the Cali Fund²⁰. After eight years of negotiation, tracking and tracing SI was deemed impractical, ineffective, and cost-inefficient.

For the PABS system, sectors, activities and benefits in scope could be identified. Focus could be put on the intended use of the R&D outcome, including existing R&D outcomes and pipelines.

Recommendation 4: Monitor public information including patents.

Through the creation of a PABS Advisory Group, a landscape analysis of existing in-scope VTDs (and those in the pipeline) could be created in a similar way as is done for the WHO bacterial priority pathogens, for which landscape analyses are published. The 2025 report maps the current and pipeline diagnostics for WHO bacterial priority pathogens, identifies gaps in access to these diagnostics, and develops a priority list for the further development of diagnostics²¹.

The PIP Advisory Group concluded that downstream use of PIP (i.e. products) could be monitored through a web-based search engine, instead of tracking the access and use of genetic sequence data²².

A keyword-based patent analysis was done for the PIP Framework at the request of the Director-General of WHO and conducted by the WIPO for PIP-relevant patents²³. They found that “A number of patent applications were identified from companies based in industrialized countries that are now co-owned by companies of developing countries.”²³. Thus, patent data can also serve as an indicator for technology transfer and could be complemented by the monitoring of market approval files or clinical trial registries.

However, patent monitoring is not suited for PABS enforcement because not all inventions actually reach the marketplace and not all inventions use IP protection (e.g. diagnostic kits). But patent analysis at a global level can be instructive in showing WHO Member States trends and changes over time and providing transparency that can be further analyzed by civil society.

Science Example

The Moderna 'betacoronavirus mRNA vaccine' patent was filed in February 2020, just weeks after the first SARS-CoV-2 genome was published²⁴. The patent does not mention SARS-CoV-2 SI, instead, it references beta coronaviruses including SARS-CoV-related viruses, other respiratory viruses, and synthetic SI. Like the Moderna betacoronavirus mRNA vaccine, many inventions are built on a mix of 'old', 'new' and synthetic SI.

If the PABS system existed before the COVID pandemic and if it monitored the intended use of R&D outcomes, this countermeasure would have been captured. If the PABS system relied on traceability at the point of data access, it would have missed this innovation.

- [COVID-19: Using DSI to design an mRNA vaccine](#)
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3. Fostering interoperability of data and databases

Interoperability of biological data, including SI, allows scientists to pursue new questions, handle complexity and make novel insights. Researchers access and connect various biological data hosted in different interconnected databases, such as DNA, protein, metabolomic, chemical interaction, or clinical trial data, to rapidly identify new or emerging pathogens, understand pathogen biology and infectious mechanisms, and develop countermeasures. For example, if a new virus is detected, early questions will be: what molecules are on the outside of the virus, what shape do they have, and what types of existing therapeutics could be used? To answer these questions, scientists need DNA, RNA, protein structural data, cell expression data, small molecule interaction predictions, and many more data types. Truly novel pathogens can only be identified by comparing them to the global corpus of data. Large, open access databases that host open and interconnected data enable these kinds of research to be fast, efficient and thorough. Re-use of data is essential, as today's new pathogen data is tomorrow's essential reference and comparator data.

On the other hand, if pathogen SI is shared in a controlled access database, it cannot be readily connected with other data and databases, nor transformed into other data types, or used in bioinformatic tools, since onwards data sharing is restricted²⁵. Controlled access databases and their built-in workbenches, or a potential WHO PABS database, cannot solve the interoperability problem, as they will not substitute for the data and functions available in today's SI database landscape. It is not possible to replace having full access to the entire scientific ecosystem of integrated open access databases.

Recommendation 5: Support additions to databases and recognize those that adapt towards PABS.

In order to foster interoperability and support PABS, WHO Member States could request that SI databases:

- Inform users about the PABS system. This information could be included in and/or linked from databases' terms of use.
- Support users in acknowledging the contributions of those who contribute samples or pathogen SI such as through the use of Open Researcher and Contributor IDs (ORCID)²⁶. The European Nucleotide Archive has piloted this approach which enables researchers of originating laboratories to "claim" their sequence data via the ORCID system²⁷. New metadata fields could provide transparency on the 'originating laboratory' (i.e. the laboratory that provided materials or SI), 'sequencing laboratory' and 'submitting institute', to highlight the roles of contributors across as many elements as possible within a data submission.

- Encourage collaboration with identified originating laboratories.
- Require metadata on the geographic location where the sample/ pathogen SI originated from²⁸.
- Where appropriate, offer a 'delayed release' model, in which data submitters can safeguard their SI privately while preparing analysis, publication and sharing with collaborative networks (such as the COMPARE Data Hubs²⁹ and the Pathoplexus system³⁰). However, it is essential that pathogen SI eventually becomes a part of the global 'open access' SI corpus. We note that this was also the initial stated intention for the GISAID database, although it has never been implemented³¹.

Databases that follow these principles could be recognized by the WHO PABS system. Participation could be incentivized through research grants.

Recommendation 6: Promote best citation practice and monitor value.

Scientific guidelines for PABS citation and acknowledgement standards in scientific publication would complement database practices. This would enable scientific publications to be used as an indicator to evaluate the PABS system to: 1) trace how pathogen SI gives rise to new knowledge, 2) measure non-monetary benefit-sharing through data submission and publications and 3) give credit to researchers and countries that share material and data. PABS acknowledgements should be easily text-mineable and enable global meta-analyses in order to offer a transparent traceable chain of pathogen SI generation and use. These analyses could then identify where samples originated from, where pathogen SI was generated, where pathogen SI was curated and where PABS-enabled research and innovation was conducted (by using the author's country information³²). This in turn could guide capacity-building in areas where there are currently fewer resources for using the PABS system to generate research outputs.

Science Example

Zoonotic diseases account for the vast majority of emerging infectious diseases worldwide. Therefore, it is key to monitor outbreaks and respond quickly³³. The open access infrastructure enables outbreak monitoring for zoonotic diseases. For example, researchers from the UK and Saudi Arabia investigated hospital outbreaks of MERS-CoV in Saudi Arabia by comparing pathogen SI from the outbreak to existing MERS-CoV genome sequences available in the GenBank database. Through their study they provided the most comprehensive list of MERS-CoV genomes thus far.

If the PABS system supports additions to databases and promotes best citation practices, such research outputs can acknowledge the originating laboratories and the PABS system in a standardized manner. If these principles and guidelines would have been established before the COVID pandemic, acknowledgement of the originating laboratories and the PABS system would have been visible globally.

- [MERS-CoV & Mpox: Using DSI to understand and fight infectious disease outbreaks](#)
DSI Scientific Network – Case Study

4. Improving access and use of pathogen SI in resource-limited settings

Online bioinformatic tools and services that rely on open access data can be used without the need for specialized hardware or software and thus can open up research opportunities³⁴. For example, one of the most common first steps in the analysis of a new SI is a BLAST search (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) against all known SI, in order to find similar SI and infer biological function for the new SI. BLAST can also help identify pathogen SI in clinical samples, help outbreak investigation and be used to monitor genetic drifts or resistance in pathogens towards existing drugs or vaccines. Widely used online open access bioinformatic tools like NCBI Nucleotide BLAST³⁵ require up-to-date access to millions of nucleotide sequences³⁶. BLAST searches typically return many hundreds of resulting similar 'hit' sequences for onward use, but only a limited number of these hits are selected and used.

If pathogen SI were largely deposited to controlled access databases, or a potential WHO PABS database, that restrict data sharing, retrieval and reuse, bioinformatic tools and databases which rely on integration of data from open access databases will become outdated quickly and eventually unusable. This applies to online bioinformatic tools (used through a web interface), certain local bioinformatic tools (installed and used in one's computer) and also databases like GISAID. This is because bioinformatic tools within GISAID, for example for sequence comparison, rely on data integration from the INSDC databases.

Controlled access to pathogen SI would therefore tend to push bioinformatic analyses more locally, requiring the local storage of millions of sequences. Storing large amounts of sequence data as well as combining large datasets locally can be very storage and compute intensive. If local hardware is limited, analyses remain confined. This would especially disadvantage researchers with limited resources or technical training, instead of improving research capabilities in low-resource settings.

Recommendation 7: Strengthen SI research capacities and infrastructure.

Improved access and use of pathogen SI, for example through bioinformatic expertise, are the starting point for in-country VTD R&D. The PABS system could be used to obtain binding commitments to increase the capacity of sequencing laboratories, in-country bioinformatic analyses and technical training in low- and middle-income countries including in inter-pandemic times by focusing on Article 5 (One Health) and Article 12(8) (additional benefit-sharing provisions) of the WHO Pandemic Agreement. The support of national or regional research consortia and projects in the Global South can have wide-reaching effects as demonstrated by ongoing efforts such as the Human Heredity and Health in Africa (H3Africa)³⁷, the Capacity Building for Bioinformatics in Latin America (CABANA) project³⁸, and the Asia Pacific Bioinformatics Network (APBioNET)³⁹. Most SI databases are located in the Global North, thus efforts are needed to strengthen research capabilities more evenly, to increase non-monetary benefit-sharing, such as for co-authorship, to create critical redundancies of data and infrastructure in times of crises, and to lay the foundation for in country VTD R&D. An encouraging sign of global sequence database strengthening has been demonstrated by the INSDC as it actively seeks to incorporate new members in the form of its Global Participation Initiative⁴⁰.

Science Example

Photo credit: CDC / Cynthia Goldsmith

The Genome Detective⁴¹ is a platform developed by an international team of scientists from Belgium, Brazil, the Netherlands, Portugal and South Africa. It offers bioinformatic tools for rapid virus identification and typing, including specialized online pipelines for viruses such as Mpox, Chikungunya or Zika viruses⁴². Researchers can upload their own SI to compare it with reference sequences and obtain information on related virus sequences and clades. These tools are based on open access reference SI databases and automated retrieval of new versions of these reference databases⁴³, ensuring that the analyses reflect the most up-to-date information. This allows researchers to perform bioinformatic analyses without having to install or maintain software and data locally. Tools like this would become outdated and unusable quickly and their development would not be possible if pathogen SI would stay confined to controlled access databases with data sharing restrictions.

5. Greater than the sum of its parts: supporting multilateralism through open access to data

For SI, the colloquialism 'the whole is greater than the sum of the parts' is highly applicable. When pathogen SI is shared with the databases, it is not only deposited but also curated through indexing and quality checks. It is also transformed into new data types, for example, pathogen DNA data flows to databases with different purposes, such as to the protein database UniProtKB, including manual quality controls like in the SwissProt section of UniProt⁴⁴, and then onwards to many other data types. Thus, being a part of the global open access SI corpus adds value to each uploaded pathogen SI as they are integrated into a broad and far-reaching ecosystem. Open access to data fundamentally supports multilateral access and is itself benefit-sharing.

Currently, until and unless the PABS system is established, all pathogen SI that is publicly available today (and not covered by other instruments) is in the scope of the CBD DSI MLM and its Cali Fund — not under the bilateral Nagoya Protocol.

No other international ABS instrument has controlled access to SI and traces access to SI databases. Instead, the PIP Framework Secretariat conducts self-reporting surveys, inviting manufacturers that have reported using PIP biological material to make their Partnership Contribution⁴⁵, and access to genetic sequence data is linked to the Partnership Contributions⁴⁶. The BBNJ Agreement (Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdictions, or High Seas Treaty) has formally recognized open access to DSI as a form of non-monetary benefit-sharing⁴⁷.

Recommendation 8: Enable mutual supportiveness with other ABS systems through open access to data.

The PABS system should closely align with the CBD DSI MLM to ensure that SI from pathogens with and without pandemic potential can be used in coherence. Otherwise most public pathogen SI will be under the CBD DSI MLM, but yet no benefits for public health and for PABS-related purposes will be achieved.

Through an open access approach, the PABS system can recognize that the value of pathogen SI is much greater when it is a part of the global, interconnected and open access SI corpus, and can establish a truly multilateral benefit-sharing and enable mutually supported interaction of ABS systems.

Science Example

Photo credit: NIAID/NIH

Skin lesions caused by the Mpox virus can resemble those caused by the herpes simplex virus or the varicella-zoster virus. To address this diagnostic challenge, multiplex PCR tests are used to distinguish between the different etiologic agents. This single diagnostic test can detect multiple viruses and therefore must effectively use SI from pathogens *without* pandemic potential which is covered by the CBD DSI MLM. This test is particularly valuable in outbreak situations or in areas with limited resources, as it can help doctors to quickly and efficiently check other common infections or co-infections⁴⁸.

Placing pathogen SI in the global open access SI corpus and ensuring mutual supportiveness between ABS systems will capture R&D on VTDs like this for benefit-sharing.

Conclusion

Traceability is a wide-ranging concept with multiple interpretations. Traceability through controlled access databases with database access tracing and data sharing restrictions risks the creation of benefit-sharing loopholes and the exclusion of pathogen SI from the existing scientific data ecosystem. Instead, traceability could harness existing systems and infrastructures to support both pandemic preparedness and response and the sharing of benefits. Traceability measures that are compatible with open access to data can facilitate a compromise that promotes both equity and science, as set out in Article 12 of the Pandemic Agreement.

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